

Holding NATO Together and Keeping the US Engaged: Strategic Implications of the Hague Summit

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HOLDING NATO TOGETHER AND KEEPING THE US ENGAGED: STRATEGIC IMPLICATIONS OF THE HAGUE SUMMIT

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Abstract

NATO's Summit of Heads of State and Heads of Government in The Hague in June 2025 took place amidst an array of challenges for the Alliance. Given Russia's ongoing invasion of Ukraine and Moscow's determination to achieve its objectives at any cost, NATO allies are under significant pressures. At the same time, the summit provided a critical moment to reflect on the future of transatlantic relations in a shifting geopolitical environment that demands a recalibration of NATO's policies.

NATO allies gathered in The Hague to reflect on how to adapt the Alliance to pressing current and future challenges and to transform internal arrangements toward more balanced and equal cooperation, particularly between European NATO allies and the United States - still NATO's primary security contributor. With Washington facing overstretched resources, dwindling stockpiles, and growing challenges from China, Russia, Iran and others, the Hague Summit marked an important moment for European NATO allies to assume greater responsibility for their own security. This commitment was reflected in the pledge to increase defense spending to 5% of GDP by 2035, aiming to ease the burden on the US while strengthening NATO's collective defense.

This GGI Analysis examines the outcomes of NATO's Hague Summit, evaluates its key decisions, and considers the challenges of implementing them. It also touches on issues that were not addressed in detail at the summit, such as persistent capability gaps, the role of the EU and its instruments in strengthening the European military-industrial base and the implications of Russia's war against Ukraine. The analysis assesses whether the summit succeeded in reinforcing NATO's defense and deterrence posture and considers the implications for the wider European security architecture and for Ukraine, whose role appeared to be sidelined at the summit but received more attention after it.

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1. Introduction

Since the beginning of the Cold War and NATO's establishment in 1949, the Alliance has remained a cornerstone of European security, grounded in transatlantic cooperation between the United States, Canada, and European states. Despite recurring criticism and claims that the Alliance became obsolete after the collapse of the Soviet Union and onwards, NATO has reasserted its relevance in the face of intensifying great power competition and the ongoing full-scale war waged by Russia against Ukraine.

In this challenging geopolitical environment, NATO continues to serve as what many perceive to be the only viable framework for collective defense and crisis management for its members. This role was repeatedly emphasized by European leaders before and during the 2025 Hague Summit, many of whom recognize the legal, fiscal and political constraints that limit the development of European defense outside NATO, thereby positioning the EU in a supportive or enabling role. The issue of building a "European pillar" of NATO was therefore also implicitly at the forefront of this Summit.

At the same time, internal frictions have resurfaced. The US' focus on China and doubts about Washington's long-term commitment to European NATO allies were among key concerns at the Summit as a result of the re-election of

Donald Trump and the uncertainty of future US policies and postures. These anxieties re-awakened memories of the 2018 Brussels Summit, where President Trump strongly criticized European allies for underinvesting in defense and threatened that the United States might not uphold its Article 5 commitments for countries falling short of the 2 % of GDP spending target.

Every NATO summit reflects the unique challenges of its moment, and the Hague Summit is no exception. While long-standing issues such as burden-sharing and strategic coherence persist, this year's meeting carried heightened stakes. In the lead-up, speculation about the Summit's potential shift from urgent discussions pertaining to European defense and security to a high-level meeting revolving around the personality of Donald Trump, alongside Ukraine's sidelined role and Zelenskyy's potential non-participation. The likelihood of a vague final communiqué highlighted deep divisions within the Alliance and critical concerns, particularly about how to respond to Russian aggression, how to advance support for Ukraine's and its membership prospects, and the allies' future relations with Russia. In addition, the summit took place in the context of Donald Trump's efforts to engage with Moscow and promote Russia-Ukraine peace negotiations without including European allies in the talks.

Table 1. NATO Summits Leading Up to The Hague (2014–2024): Geopolitical Contexts, Agendas, and Key Outcomes

Summit	Geopolitical Context	NATO's Agenda or Priorities	Key Points of Disagreement	Results
Wales (2014)³	Russia's illegal annexation of Crimea. War begins in the separate areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine.	Reassure Eastern allies. Launch of Readiness Action Plan. Increase defense spending.	Diverging threat perception. Policies towards Russia. Burden-sharing tensions.	2% GDP defense spending pledge by 2024. Very High Readiness Joint Task Force (VJTF) created; ⁴ Enhanced forward presence commitment.
Warsaw (2016)⁵	Continued Russian aggression. Instability in Syria and the Middle East. Terrorist attacks in Europe.	Increased allied presence in Baltic states and Poland. Strengthening EU-NATO cooperation.	Concerns (by some members) over provoking Russia. Ways of strengthening NATO's deterrence.	Enhanced Forward Presence (EFP) deployments agreed; ⁶ Ballistic missile defense (BMD) declared operational Signature of the 2016 EU-NATO Joint Declaration. ⁷

³ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2022) "Wales Summit Declaration," [NATO](#), 5 September 2014.

⁴ Allied Land Command, "NATO Response Force," [accessed](#) 16 July 2025.

⁵ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2016) "Warsaw Summit Communiqué," [NATO](#), 9 July 2016.

⁶ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2016) "NATO's military presence in the east of the Alliance," [accessed](#) 16 July 2025

⁷ North Atlantic Treaty Organization and European Union (2016) "Joint Declaration by the President of the European Council, the President of the European Commission and the Secretary General of NATO," [NATO](#), 8 July 2016.

<p>Brussels (2017)*⁸</p>	<p>Shifting transatlantic relations amid Trump's election as the US president.</p> <p>Russian war against Ukraine and hybrid threats against transatlantic community continue.</p> <p>Ongoing terrorism concerns.</p> <p>Montenegro's membership.</p>	<p>Burden-sharing.</p> <p>Counterterrorism.</p> <p>NATO's role in the coalition against ISIS.</p>	<p>Increased defense spending and criticism from Trump.</p> <p>Trump undermining NATO's Article 5.</p>	<p>NATO formally joins anti-ISIS coalition.</p> <p>Allies recommit to defense spending goals.</p>
<p>Brussels (2018)⁹</p>	<p>US demands higher European defense spending.</p> <p>Persistent threat Russia's invasion of Ukraine.</p> <p>Russia's hybrid threats.</p>	<p>Burden-sharing; modernization.</p> <p>Counterterrorism.</p> <p>Strengthening command structure.</p> <p>EU-NATO cooperation.</p>	<p>Trump's threats regarding US commitment to NATO and unwillingness to protect European allies.</p> <p>Disputes over fair burden-sharing.</p>	<p>Spending increases reaffirmed.</p> <p>New North Atlantic Command established.</p> <p>Signature of the 2018 EU-NATO Joint Declaration.¹⁰</p>

⁸ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2017) "NATO leaders agree to do more to fight terrorism and ensure fairer burden-sharing," [NATO](#), 25 May 2017.

⁹ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2018) "Brussels Summit Declaration," [NATO](#), 11 July 2018.

¹⁰ North Atlantic Treaty Organization and European Union (2016) *Joint Declaration on EU-NATO Cooperation by the President of the European Council, the President of the European Commission, and the Secretary General of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization*, [NATO](#), 10 July 2018.

London (2019)¹¹	Türkiye's intervention in Syria. Unpredictability of the US policies under Trump. Rising China security threat.	NATO 70th anniversary. Addressing China threat. Counterterrorism. Boosting resilience.	Macron's "brain dead" NATO comment; ¹² Türkiye's S-400 purchase from Russia and surrounding tensions. ¹³	Recognition of China as a challenge. Commitment to unity despite internal divergences.
Brussels (2021)¹⁴	US President Biden reassuring America's back and commitment to NATO and multilateralism stands. Continued Russia's war against Ukraine.	NATO 2030 Agenda launch. Climate change. Resilience. Tech innovation.	Divergence on China policy. Clashes over defense spending progress.	NATO 2030 Agenda endorsed. ¹⁵ Climate change integrated into NATO's agenda.
Madrid (2022)¹⁶	Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine. Finland and Sweden apply for NATO membership.	New Strategic Concept naming Russia as threat, China as challenge. Strengthening NATO's Eastern flank.	Türkiye's/Hungary's opposition to Sweden's and Finland's membership. Defense investment gaps.	2022 NATO Strategic Concept adopted; ¹⁷ Finland and Sweden received an invitation to join NATO. Major posture reinforcement in Eastern European NATO members.

¹¹ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2019) "London Declaration issued by the Heads of State and Government participating in the meeting of the North Atlantic Council in London 3–4 December 2019," [NATO](#), 4 December 2019.

¹² BBC News (2019) "NATO alliance experiencing brain death, says Macron," [BBC News](#), 7 November 2019.

¹³ International Institute for Strategic Studies (IISS) (2019) "Turkey, the S-400 and the F-35," [IISS](#), August 2019.

¹⁴ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2021) "Brussels Summit Communiqué," [NATO](#), 14 June 2021.

¹⁵ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2020) "NATO 2030: Making a Strong Alliance Even Stronger," [NATO](#), accessed 16 July 2025

¹⁶ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2022) "Madrid Summit Declaration" [NATO](#), 29 June 2022.

¹⁷ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2022) "NATO 2022 Strategic Concept," [NATO](#), 29 June 2022.

<p>Vilnius (2023)¹⁸</p>	<p>Russia’s war against Ukraine evolving into a protracted conflict.</p> <p>Ukraine’s push for membership.</p> <p>Persistent Russian hybrid attacks.</p>	<p>Support for Ukraine.</p> <p>Defense production ramp-up.</p> <p>Boosting NATO’s Eastern Flank deterrence.</p> <p>Cybersecurity and tech resilience.</p>	<p>NATO membership invitation for Ukraine.</p> <p>Disagreements on membership timeline and future of the NATO-Ukraine cooperation</p>	<p>Creation of the NATO-Ukraine Council;¹⁹</p> <p>Approval of the long-term Comprehensive Assistance Package (CAP) for Ukraine;²⁰</p> <p>—defense industry modernization.</p>
<p>Washington (2024)²¹</p>	<p>War in Ukraine</p> <p>US and European elections.</p> <p>Global geopolitical fragmentation war in Gaza continues, China’s rising aggressiveness around Taiwan, US-China competition over advanced technology</p> <p>AI, quantum., critical raw materials, rise and expansion of BRICS and growing challenges to rules-based international order.</p>	<p>Sustain Ukraine support.</p> <p>Transatlantic unity; defense spending 2% implementation.</p> <p>Tech and resilience.</p> <p>Enhancing NATO’s Indo-Pacific partnerships.</p>	<p>US-Europe burden-sharing debates.</p> <p>Ukraine membership pathway ambiguity.</p>	<p>Renewed Ukraine support commitments (Ukraine Compact and bilateral security agreements with Ukraine);²²</p> <p>Defense production agreements.</p> <p>Posture adjustments on the Eastern flank.</p>

¹⁸ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2023) “*Vilnius Summit Communiqué*,” [NATO](#), 11 July 2023.

¹⁹ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2023) “*NATO-Ukraine Council*,” [NATO](#), accessed 16 July 2025.

²⁰ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2023) *Comprehensive Assistance Package for Ukraine*, [NATO](#), accessed 16 July 2025.

²¹ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2024) “*Washington Summit Declaration*,” [NATO](#), 10 July 2024.

²² President of Ukraine Official Website (2024) “*Endorsement of the Ukraine Compact Marks the Solemn Conclusion of the NATO Anniversary Summit*,” [President of Ukraine](#), 12 July 2024.

**The 2017 NATO gathering in Brussels (25 May 2017) was formally a Meeting of NATO Heads of State and Government, not a full summit. However, it was crucial for understanding the evolution of NATO and its subsequent summits, as it marked the opening of NATO's new headquarters, included a leaders' discussion on burden-sharing and counterterrorism, and featured President Trump's demands for increased European defense spending, which shaped debates at the 2018 Brussels Summit.*

The Hague Summit thus served as a key test of NATO's cohesion at a critical juncture. This GGI analysis assesses the outcomes and implications of the Summit on European security, focusing on the Alliance's ability to deliver credible burden-sharing, reinforce transatlantic unity, continue supporting Ukraine amid Russia's invasion, and chart a path forward amid rising uncertainty about continued US engagement and a looming Russian threat, as some intelligence services believe the Russian Federation could soon be capable of attacking NATO or one of its members and being able to achieve success.²³ It also examines potential limitations related to the decisions made during the Summit, despite the clear ambition shown by European NATO members to strengthen the Alliance and their own defense capabilities.

2. The 2025 Hague Summit: Decisions and Divergences

The European allies' key objective at the summit was to persuasively communicate to the Trump

administration that they are working towards a more equal partnership within NATO, wherein the Europeans will invest significantly more into European conventional defense.²⁴ This was to serve the (second) objective to secure transatlantic cohesion on deterrence, despite Donald Trump's well-known skepticism towards the NATO alliance and US long-term commitment to European security within NATO. While these goals dominated the summit's agenda, they came at the expense of dealing with urgent questions related to Ukraine's security, one of the most pressing issues for European security writ large. Rather tellingly and in contrast to the last two summits, Ukraine's role at the Summit was limited to one of an observer.

Against the background of the tensions with Trump over NATO during his first term, European leaders had started deliberations on a potential second Trump presidency already ahead of the US elections. The selection of Mark Rutte as new NATO Secretary-General, who had managed to maintain a functional relationship with Trump during his tenure as Dutch prime-minister, can be seen as a preliminary

²³ Frank Gardner and Tessa Wong (2025) "Russia May Attack NATO in Next Four Years, German Defence Chief Warns," [BBC News](#), 1 June 2025.

²⁴ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2025) Pre-summit press conference by NATO Secretary General Mark Rutte ahead of the NATO Summit in The Hague; 23 June 2025, [NATO](#), 23 June 2025.

attempt by the European governments to maintain a somewhat productive dialogue with Trump. Once in office, and following the US elections, Rutte's key goal was to keep the US administration committed to NATO and ensure Trump's participation in The Hague, and all preparations ahead of the summit were subordinate to that goal. A first priority for Rutte was therefore to forge consensus among the NATO allies on the need to significantly increase the national defense budgets.

SG Rutte succeeded in convincing the member states (with exceptions, such as Spain) to embrace the goal to spend 5% of their GDP on defense. The percentage was brought up by Trump, even though he claimed that the US should be exempted from this goal as the US "has supported NATO for so long".²⁵ To signal their political will of a new burden-sharing deal, NATO allies prepared an outline to achieve this level through gradual increase until 2035. While 3,5% of GDP should be geared towards "hard defense", the allies agreed to spend 1,5% on defense-related issues such as enhancing military mobility, cyber security, and the protection of critical infrastructure. This pre-emptive messaging towards the US administration worked out at the NATO summit, which ended without open tensions. When asked to clarify his stance on NATO's mutual defense clause, Trump argued "I wouldn't be

here" if he didn't stand with the alliance.²⁶ In addition, the members discussed how to enhance the defense industrial base and transatlantic cooperation on the topic. European leaders pointed out that the decision to significantly increase their defense budgets was less a result of pressure from the US administration, but rather out of necessity to address Russia's threat to NATO.²⁷

During the summit, the almost exclusive focus on appeasing Trump, however, came at the expense of discussions over Ukraine's security, including questions of the role NATO should (continue to) play in supporting Ukraine in its defense against Russia; how NATO allies could potentially provide security guarantees for Ukraine after a ceasefire; and concrete steps towards Ukraine's path to NATO membership. In an effort to reduce the potential for tensions with the US president, who is opposed to Ukraine's NATO membership, these topics were intentionally left out of the summit's agenda. This in itself has been the key divergence amongst the allies; not only between many European governments and the US administration, but also among the Europeans themselves. While the majority of European NATO allies continue to support Ukraine's membership, Hungarian prime-minister Orban did not hide his clear opposition to this goal. Given President Trump's position, the reference to Ukraine's

²⁵ Financial Times (2025), Nato summit as it happened: North American and European leaders agree on 5% defence spending target; Trump affirms US commitment to Article 5, [Financial Times](#), 25 June 2025.

²⁶ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2025) The Hague Summit Declaration, [NATO](#), 25 June 2025.

²⁷ Ibid, the [Hague Summit Declaration](#) (2025)

“irreversible path” to NATO membership of the 2024 summit communiqué was not included in the 2025 communiqué, but it was also not openly questioned at the summit. Noteworthy, a meeting of the NATO-Ukraine Council, which aims to “advance political dialogue”, including Ukraine's aspiration for membership, was held. Rutte's remarks that all NATO allies are “totally committed” to continue to support Ukraine may be overly optimistic, but several members have indeed pledged to sustain their military support.

Even though it has been a diplomatic balancing act, NATO continues to play a key role in supporting Ukraine's defense, which has also not been openly put into question by the Trump administration. Since 2024, the NATO Security Assistance and Training for Ukraine (NSATU) is the key mechanism for coordinating the logistics of the Western military assistance to Ukraine.²⁸ While US personnel remain heavily involved in these operations, the contributions of European military staff have been increasing significantly over time. This illustrates a slow but gradual shift towards European primary responsibility for military aid to Ukraine. In addition, the Trump administration has passed the lead of the Ukraine Defense Contact Group,²⁹ which had been chaired by former Secretary of Defense, Lloyd Austin, to European allies. The group, which consists of more than 50 countries, has been the main platform for coordinating military assistance to Ukraine since 2022.

²⁸ North Atlantic Treaty Organization, “NATO Security Assistance and Training for Ukraine,” Supreme Headquarters Allied Powers Europe (SHAPE), [accessed](#) 18 July 2025

Since February 2025, it is chaired by the ministers of defense of the UK and Germany, and regularly uses the NATO headquarters for its meetings (even though NATO is not the official host). Experiences of this responsibility-shifting with regards to Ukraine support may be useful for a future shifting of responsibilities within NATO and the efforts to create a stronger “European pillar” within the organization.

The fact that Ukraine support did not play a major role at the NATO summit was primarily the result of the unclear stance of the Trump administration on the topic. Predicting the future of American aid to Ukraine remains difficult as President Trump's policy stances towards Ukraine have been subject to erratic change since January. The Trump administration has continued to provide some of the assistance that was granted during the Biden Presidency (with congressional authorization) in April 2024, although it had temporarily suspended some of the military assistance and intelligence-sharing in February and reportedly also halted some shipments in July. These events have diminished trust in US reliability and predictability, not only with regards to Ukraine support, but also - indirectly - with regards to the US commitment to NATO defense more generally.

Trump's primary goal has been to achieve a rapid ceasefire or peace agreement between Ukraine and Russia, potentially at the expense of Ukraine's territorial integrity. Before the summit, Trump has been reluctant to

²⁹ U.S. Department of Defense (2024) “Fact Sheet on Efforts of Ukraine Defense Contact Group – National Armaments Directors,” [U.S. Department of Defense](#), 6 September 2024.

publicly (or privately) side with Ukraine in the conflict. He does not seem to share the view that supporting Ukraine's defense is in the strategic interest of the US, a stance that has been held by a significant number of members of Congress, including Republicans. Trump has repeatedly made clear that he expects the European allies to take over the primary responsibility for assisting Ukraine, including military assistance. While some European governments have gradually stepped up their efforts, they also pointed out that the role of the US, at least in a supporting role, will remain important for the time being (e.g. in key areas like intelligence, surveillance, target acquisition and reconnaissance).

As a result, the question under which circumstances a continued US engagement in supporting Ukraine could be secured was among the key topics in the discussions between several European heads of government and Trump since January. European allies were also concerned that the Trump administration may veto the purchase of US weaponry (e.g., air defense systems) from US manufacturers to be shipped to Ukraine (there are usually restrictions on the resale of weapons or systems containing components or technology originating from the US).

Some of these issues were partly addressed after the NATO summit. On 10th July, Trump announced an arrangement in which NATO would purchase defense equipment (including

the Patriot missile defense system) from the US for Ukraine. In parallel, the German and Norwegian governments announced that they would purchase new Patriot systems from the US. As of August, the new system, the Prioritized Ukraine Requirements List (PURL) initiative, seems to be operational. After the Ukrainian government submits a list of required weaponry and munitions, the US government accordingly drafts a package of defense materials (around 500 million USD) that are available for purchase. European (or non-European) governments - not NATO - can then agree to take on these costs, which has occurred three times since July.³⁰ The linchpin is NATO's Security Assistance and Training for Ukraine (NSATU), which coordinates the creation of the lists and delivers the materials to Ukraine via NATO logistics channels.

While the new system puts the financial burden heavily on the European allies, it is an important avenue to secure the continued flow of much-needed US equipment to Ukraine, in addition to the deliveries from other partners. At the same time, it reduces the likelihood that Trump will request Congress for a new aid package that goes beyond the delivery of aid that was approved in 2024. Despite Trump's reluctance, a bipartisan group of US senators continues to advocate for a new 54 billion USD aid package.³¹

Similar to the Ukraine-US Mineral Resources Agreement of April 2025³²,

³⁰ North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2025), "Germany to fund \$500m PURL package for Ukraine", [accessed](#) 25 August 2025.

³¹ Reuters (2025), "US Senate committee backs more Ukraine funding, following Trump shift on aid", 31 July 2025, [accessed](#) 25 August 2025.

³² Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine (2025) Agreement between the Government of Ukraine and the

the PURL initiative seems to indicate that Trump is willing to allow continued aid to Ukraine, provided it aligns with US business interests and that European allies assume the bulk of the financial responsibility for military assistance. This transactional approach stands in stark contrast to that of the Biden administration, which was based particularly on geopolitical considerations and a commitment to upholding a rules-based international order.

The likelihood of advancing another measure to increase pressure on Russia, the potential US expansion of sanctions against the Russian Federation, remains unclear. For months a group of senators had been drafting a sanctions package against countries that have expanded their trade with Russia, particularly in the field of energy resources. Trump seems to have viewed such a step as an obstacle to negotiations with Vladimir Putin. However, following a phone conversation with President Putin that Trump described as “disappointing”, the US president threatened to impose harsh sanctions on Russia as well as secondary tariffs against countries that continue to trade with Russia (particularly China and India) in case that Russia would not “stop the killing” in Ukraine and increase its efforts in ceasefire negotiations with Ukraine.

Following the Trump-Putin meeting in Alaska in August, Trump has not repeated the threat of expanded sanctions against Russia, but he has announced increased tariffs on India for

its purchase of Russian energy resources. Overall, it is unclear to what extent the Trump administration will continue its negotiations efforts, or whether it will gradually disentangle itself from the process.

Leaving out Ukraine as a key agenda item at the NATO summit was an attempt by Europeans to accommodate the Trump administration’s preferences and to avoid a contentious issue. At the same time, it is an acknowledgment of the governments that Ukraine’s security is not directly interchangeable with NATO security as long as Ukraine is not a member. While the NATO allies in the communiqué “reaffirm their enduring sovereign commitments to provide support to Ukraine, whose security contributes to ours (...)”³³ and have in the past years provided aid to Ukraine, no NATO member has so far been willing to offer direct military intervention in support of Ukraine. They regard national defense as a priority and several governments have been unwilling to share defense systems with Ukraine that they consider key for their national security (e.g., air defense systems such as Patriot). Even though this is not news for Ukraine, the NATO summit was a sobering reminder that solidarity among states - and not only the US - should not be taken for granted. As a result, Ukraine aid will likely continue in the framework of coalitions of the willing and through the PURL initiative.

Besides largely leaving out Ukraine, the summit’s communiqué also did not address a number of strategic issues

Government of the United States of America on the Establishment of a United States - Ukraine Reconstruction Investment Fund, Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 30 April 2025

³³ Ibid, the [Hague Summit Declaration](#) (2025)

relevant to NATO, including drafting a NATO Russia strategy; addressing China's role in supporting Russia's war and as a threat to transatlantic security overall; and expanding NATO's relationship with partners in the Indo-Pacific.³⁴

In addition, the US future military presence in Europe remains unclear. The appointment of a four-star general for the post of the SACEUR and commander of the US European Command is a signal that the US will continue its significant engagement in Europe.³⁵ However, the future size of US military capabilities remains unclear and is currently discussed in the US Global Force Posture Review that will be presented later this year. There seem to be different opinions on this matter within the administration, with some (former) political appointees arguing in favor of significant cuts to the US presence in Europe,³⁶ while some military commanders have raised doubts about such developments.³⁷

³⁴ Torrey Taussig (2025) "Four Fundamental Questions the NATO Summit Did Not Answer," [Atlantic Council](#), 27 June 2025.

³⁵ United States Senate (2025) Hearings to examine the nominations of Vice Admiral Charles B. Cooper II, USN, to be admiral and Commander, United States Central Command, and Lieutenant General Alexis G. Grynkeiwich, USAF, to be general and Commander, United States European Command and Supreme Allied Commander, Europe, both of the Department of Defense, [United States Senate, Committee on Armed Services](#), 24 June 2025.

3. European NATO Allies' Defense Posture After The Hague: Time to Act Alone?

The Hague Summit's narrow focus on transatlantic burden-sharing and maintaining cohesion with the US, while sidelining urgent discussions on Ukraine's security, also underscores a deeper question facing European NATO members: how to strengthen their own defense posture amid uncertainty about continued American commitment? As debates over Ukraine's future intersect with Europe's long-term security challenges, the summit highlighted that building credible European defense capabilities is not only vital for supporting Ukraine but also essential for NATO's ability to deter future threats and adapt to a shifting security landscape.

With the 5% goal, which some perceive as overly ambitious or unrealistic to sustain,³⁸ European allies have signaled their ambition to take greater responsibility for European security. However, it also reflects deeper doubts

³⁶ Jennifer Kavanagh and Dan Caldwell (2025) *Aligning Global Military Posture with U.S. Interests, Defense Priorities*, 9 July 2025

³⁷ John Vandiver (2025) "I don't think there's going to be a change,' general says of US military presence in Europe," [Stars and Stripes](#), 25 June 2025.

³⁸ Iana Maisuradze and Paul Taylor (eds.) (2025) *Countdown to the NATO Summit in The Hague: Priorities and Expectations in 2025*, [European Policy Centre](#), 19 June 2025.

about American reliability and the need to decrease the allies' dependence on the US. If European NATO members fail with the messaging and implementation of this ambitious agenda, it could lead to further rifts in transatlantic relations in the future. The Hague Summit, therefore, underscores the need to strengthen European defense capabilities and the defense industrial base to address both short-term threats and long-term strategic challenges, including Russia's war against Ukraine.³⁹ These capabilities refer to a variety of quantitative and qualitative measures related to weapon systems and ammunition, personnel, logistics, and overall operational readiness. However, it is important to note that the increases in defense budgets do not automatically translate into meaningful progress and improvements in these areas.

Despite the sensitivity of the issue of increased defense spending, and given the diverging national priorities across European states, according to a recent survey, a majority of respondents in several European states support higher defense spending.⁴⁰ This trend is not irreversible and will likely be contested at the national level across European NATO members. Moreover, uncertainties over the future policies of the US administration and the ongoing invasion of Ukraine provide additional

impetus for growing support for increased military expenditures. In this respect, recent polls also indicate that the majority of respondents have favorable views on NATO, which also highlights its relevance in countering threats towards democracies.⁴¹

3.1 Intra-European and Transatlantic Consensus Building after the Summit

One of the summit's primary goals was to strengthen NATO's deterrence through increased defense spending and enhancing the military-industrial base of its members for capability development.⁴² It remains to be seen if the pledges made will indeed lead to actual results, as much will depend on the timely implementation of the commitments. There are several challenges associated with that, including ensuring coherence within the alliance; preventing "creative accounting" in defense budgets; Donald Trump's ambiguous stance on Russia; and the uncertainty over the future US role in European security.

Spain effectively opted out of the 5% pledge. This could set a precedent for other countries to follow Madrid's example or to delay or avoid fulfilling their commitments, seeking potential opt-outs. It also remains unclear what

³⁹ Oana Lungescu (2025) "NATO's High-Stakes Summit: Buying Time to Fill the Gaps," [Royal United Services Institute \(RUSI\)](#), 23 June 2025.

⁴⁰ Ivan Krastev and Mark Leonard (2025) *Trump's European Revolution*, [European Council on Foreign Relations \(ECFR\)](#) Policy Brief, 23 June 2025.

⁴¹ Moira Fagan, Sneha Gubbala, and Jacob Poushter (2025) *NATO Viewed Favorably Across 13 Member Nations*, [Pew Research Center](#), 23 June 2025.

⁴² North Atlantic Treaty Organization (2025) "Deterrence and Defence," [NATO](#), accessed 16 July 2025.

kind of an agreement was reached between Spain and NATO allies to secure support for the final communiqué, not to mention the fact that the language of the document was adjusted from “we commit” to “allies commit” to secure Madrid’s approval.⁴³ The case of Spain could seriously hinder efforts to strengthen European security, especially given also the lack of a shared threat perception across Europe.⁴⁴ Not all European NATO allies view a potential Russian attack on NATO as imminent, while others see addressing illegal migration and climate change as priorities.

It is equally important that NATO members do not push their national projects and frame them as ones that correspond to the 5% NATO defense spending target, especially regarding the 1,5% target for spending on defense-related projects, critical infrastructure, cybersecurity, and similar areas. This portion of funding leaves much room for maneuver by NATO allies and for creative accounting. They might prioritize national infrastructure projects that, for example, end up unsuitable for military mobility, or spend money on issues that do not contribute to NATO’s wider defense and deterrence but instead amount to national civilian expenditures. The 1,5% target should therefore be further clarified regarding what qualifies as defense spending and

should be mutually agreed upon between individual NATO members and the Alliance. This should be done if European allies are truly committed to bolstering their capacity to act independently and ensuring that funding is used appropriately to meet NATO’s goals and capability targets.

Regarding the US, an obstacle in forging a stronger deterrence posture against Russia is the ambiguous stance of Donald Trump towards Russia. This is reflected in the rather weak language on Russia in the NATO communiqué.

While Russia was actively striking Ukrainian cities and killing civilians,⁴⁵ Trump hesitated to answer whether the US would sell Patriot air defense systems and missiles to Kyiv and mentioned he had been “considering” that option after meeting Zelenskyy at the sidelines of the Hague Summit.⁴⁶ Given that Europe’s rearmament will take at least 5 years,⁴⁷ if not for a decade, it was crucial for the US to signal openness to allowing Ukraine and European NATO allies to purchase these systems without additional hurdles. In the eyes of external observers, the 5% commitment may appear shaky and reversible, with only a “coalition of the willing” genuinely interested in meeting this target. The rifts between the US and European NATO members are not fully resolved, sending a signal to Russia and China

⁴³ France 24 (2025) “Spain strikes deal with NATO to be exempt from 5 percent defence spending target,” [France 24](#), 22 June 2025.

⁴⁴ Mihai Chihaiia (2024) “What Europe thinks about European security and defense,” [European Policy Centre](#), 24 October 2024.

⁴⁵ Yuliia Taradiuk (2025) “Smashing previous monthly record, Russia launches 5,337 kamikaze

drones against Ukraine during June,” [Kyiv Independent](#), 30 June 2025.

⁴⁶ The Guardian (2025) “Ukraine war briefing: Trump says US looking at providing Kyiv with more Patriot missiles,” [The Guardian](#), 26 June 2025

⁴⁷ Rudy Ruitenberg (2025) “Mind the Gaps: Europe’s To-Do List for Defence Without the US,” [Defense News](#), 25 February 2025.

that transatlantic relations are still fragile. The Hague Summit did not deliver a clear division of labor or a vision for navigating transatlantic security, nor did it articulate a coherent strategy for NATO to remain effective should the US withdraw or disengage from Europe.⁴⁸

It needs to be pointed out that the summit took place at a time when it remains unclear which US assets and capabilities may be withdrawn from Europe, and overall unclarity about the US global posture, including in the Indo-Pacific and the Middle East.⁴⁹ As pointed out above, discussions over this are ongoing in the US. For European NATO allies, understanding this debate is still vital for prioritizing and strategizing which capabilities should be their focus, given that many European allies heavily rely on American strategic enablers, for instance, ISTAR, air-to-air refueling, as well as other contributions such as US troop presence, involvement in command-and-control structures, air defense systems, and deep strike capabilities.⁵⁰

While the 5% pledge created the impression that the US will continue to remain committed to NATO's collective defense, it also increased the pressure on European allies to fully implement the ambitious defense agenda. Not least, the US administration will closely

follow progress in the allies' efforts to meet the new "burden-sharing" model. This refers, first, to securing the financing needed for higher defense spending. Every government will have to push through the 5% goal domestically, often against competing national policy priorities. It remains to be seen to what extent EU instruments outlined in the "Readiness 2030" plan to support defense funding will be useful in this context. Irrespective of the defense budget, it will be important for European NATO allies to gradually fill gaps in military capabilities and capacities where they rely heavily on the United States.

A question that may arrive sooner rather than later is to what extent the US defense industry will be involved in European defense acquisition. The 2025 communiqué refers to a "shared commitment to rapidly expand transatlantic defense industrial cooperation" and a goal "to eliminate defense trade barriers among Allies." So far, most NATO members have relied on US products for two-thirds (64%) of their arms imports between 2020 and 2024,⁵¹ a ratio that many European governments want to change significantly. This issue might lead to tensions with US administrations in the future. In addition, a continuation of Trump's tariffs policy and potential further escalation will likely undermine the political goal to enhance

⁴⁸ Camille Grand (2025) 'The end of the "imperial republic" and the future of the transatlantic alliance,' [The Brookings Institution](#), 23 June 2025.

⁴⁹ Giuseppe Spatafora (2025) Fit for purpose? Reforming NATO in the age of Trump 2.0, [European Union Institute for Security Studies \(EUISS\)](#), 4 June 2025.

⁵⁰ Ben Barry, Douglas Barrie et al. (2025) *Defending Europe Without the United States: Costs and*

Consequences, [International Institute for Strategic Studies \(IISS\)](#), 15 May 2025

⁵¹ Katarina Djokic (2025) 'Are the European NATO states moving towards self-reliance in arms procurement? A Q&A with Katarina Djokic', [SIPRI Commentary](#), 19 March 2025.

transatlantic cooperation in the defense sector.⁵²

Table 2: NATO Hague Summit: Commitments Made and Challenges Ahead

Item of Discussion	Action Agreed/Deferred	Opportunities and Impact	Limitations and Remaining Challenges
Increasing Defense Spending	<p>Commitment to invest 5% of GDP annually on defense by 2035, split as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.5% on core defense • 1.5% on defense-and security-related investments <p>Commitment to submit annual plans to demonstrate progress toward the target, with a review scheduled for 2029.</p>	<p>New burden-sharing deal to attain a more equal partnership within NATO, as well as to strengthen NATO's collective security.</p> <p>Reflects European NATO members' ambition / necessity to take greater responsibility for European security amid Russia's continued war against Ukraine and doubts about Washington's long-term commitment to European NATO members.</p>	<p>Absence of full European consensus on the defense spending pledge (e.g. Spain).</p> <p>US self-exemption from the defense spending pledge.</p> <p>Political and fiscal challenges to the feasibility of reaching 5% of GDP.</p> <p>Lack of clarity on who will evaluate compliance with spending targets.</p>

⁵² Alexandra Brzozowski (2025) "With Trump's trade war threats, EU leaders prepare to retaliate," [Euractiv](#), 3 February 2025.

			<p>Lack of clarity on what constitutes the additional 1.5% in defense spending (risk of ambiguous categorization and creative accounting).</p> <p>Absence of a clear roadmap for strengthening the European pillar within NATO.</p>
Increasing Defense Production	<p>Commitment to rapidly expand transatlantic defense industrial cooperation, to harness emerging technology and to promote defense industrial cooperation.</p>	<p>Release of the first public Updated Defence Production Action Plan which outlines NATO's commitment to aggregate demand, boost capacity and strengthen engagement with industry.</p> <p>Reflects allies' resolve and necessity to strengthen NATO's defense industrial base and capacities, in line and expanding upon previous commitments made in Vilnius (2023) and Washington (2024).</p>	<p>Lack of substantive discussion on persistent capability gaps</p> <p>Uncertainties over how EU's "Readiness 2030" plan will integrate with transatlantic defense cooperation efforts.</p> <p>Uncertainties over the extent of US defense industry involvement in European defense manufacturing and procurement.</p>
Deterrence and Defense	<p>Reaffirmation of Collective Defence (commitment labelled as "ironclad", as in the 2024 Washington Summit Declaration).</p> <p>Lack of substantive discussion on NATO's strategic approach to Russia (contrary to what was stated in the 2024 Washington Summit Declaration).</p> <p>Lack of substantive discussion on China, and partners in the Indo-Pacific.</p>	<p>Signals transatlantic cohesion on deterrence, despite Trump's skepticism of NATO and doubts about US commitment to European security.</p> <p>The new defense pledge can be seen as the first step toward addressing "the long-term threat posed by Russia to Euro-Atlantic security" and could serve as a basis for crafting a comprehensive NATO strategy and approach to Russia.</p>	<p>Persisting low trust in US reliability regarding NATO deterrence.</p> <p>Lack of clarity over future US military presence (assets, capabilities) in Europe.</p> <p>Absence of a clear division of labor and vision for managing transatlantic security.</p>

			<p>Absence of a coherent NATO strategy in case of US withdrawal or disengagement from Europe.</p> <p>Divisions within NATO over how to respond to Russian aggression.</p> <p>Lack of stronger and unified deterrence posture against Russia and China.</p>
Support for Ukraine	<p>Reaffirmation of Ukraine's security as contributing to NATO's (as in the 2024 Washington Summit Declaration), but lack of substantive discussion about Ukraine's defense and NATO membership path.</p> <p>Ukraine's limited role as an observer in the Summits' overall agenda in contrast to its participation during NATO summits in Vilnius (2023) and Washington (2024).</p>	<p>Signals the continuing shift toward European allies taking primary responsibility for assisting Ukraine.</p>	<p>Divisions within NATO over how to advance support for Ukraine and its membership prospects</p> <p>Uncertainty over the terms of continued US support to Ukraine</p> <p>Risk of a significant financial burden on European NATO members to acquire US weaponry for Ukraine support.</p>

3.2 The Role of the EU in a Path Towards a Stronger European Pillar within NATO

Despite the assurances at the NATO summit, the question to what extent the Trump administration would be willing to act resolutely in case of a Russian aggression against a NATO member (e.g., a small-scale invasion in the Baltics) will remain a concern for many European governments. Given the unpredictability of the current US government, the other NATO allies

should at least prepare for a scenario in which they would have to act independently. At the same time, there is an awareness that the creation of independent defense structures (e.g. command and control) outside of NATO would require much time, significant political will and resources. European NATO allies remain heavily dependent on the US in certain capabilities, and the summit demonstrated their efforts to maintain unity, often appearing nearly subordinate to US preferences. As a result of these constraints, most governments prefer the creation of a stronger European pillar within NATO. In these efforts, the EU could play a

critical role. It has a valuable potential to support a stronger Europe's defense industry and capability production, and European leaders consistently emphasize the EU's ability to enable and incentivize EU NATO member states to meet Alliance's targets.⁵³

After the summit, NATO allies' priority should be to revive domestic production, maintain constructive dialogue with the defense industry, and streamline legislation to close the gap between the urgent need for rapid manufacturing, with Ukraine's frontline needs in mind, and the long-term objectives of European rearmament to deter potential attacks on NATO. European NATO members have the economic capacity to strengthen their own military production while ensuring stable support for Ukraine, provided there is a political will and a clear strategy towards handling Russia's menace.⁵⁴ As the EU's Foreign Policy Chief Kaja Kallas stated prior to the Hague Summit, Russia has spent more on defense than all the EU members combined, therefore it is a high time for European NATO allies to step-up, if they are willing to be better prepared for a potential direct military confrontation with Russia, as well as to be able to respond to the changing battlefield

dynamics in Ukraine.⁵⁵ Establishing additional joint European enterprises focused on military capabilities and projects, as well as coordinating joint procurement, will be critical. Particular attention should be paid to reinvigorating already existing and new EU mechanisms and instruments to ensure their coherent use. This includes mechanism and frameworks such as Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), the European Defence Fund (EDF), the European Peace Facility (EPF), the Act in Support of Ammunition Production (ASAP), and the European Defence Industry Reinforcement through Common Procurement Act (EDIRPA).

If European allies are serious about strengthening their defense capabilities, NATO-EU collaboration must advance to a new level, even if the process takes time. Since Russia's full-scale invasion, the EU has proposed and/or adopted several documents, strategies, frameworks, and instruments to contribute to European defense and NATO's broader capability goals, including the White Paper for European Defence - Readiness 2030,⁵⁶ the ReArm Europe Plan,⁵⁷ the Security Action for Europe (SAFE) instrument,⁵⁸ and the EU's Defense and Industrial

⁵³ European Commission (EC) (2025) "Commissioner Kubilius's speech at the European Defence Agency Annual Conference," [EC](#), 22 January 2025.

⁵⁴ Ondrej Ditrych, Steven Everts et al. (2025) *Unpowering Russia: How the EU can counter and undermine the Kremlin*, [European Union Institute for Security Studies \(EUISS\)](#), Chaillot Paper No. 178, 22 May 2025.

⁵⁵ European External Action Service (EEAS) (2025) "Remarks by High Representative/Vice-President Kaja Kallas at the EP Plenary Session key debate on

the upcoming NATO summit on 24-26 June 2025," [EEAS](#), 18 June 2025.

⁵⁶ European Commission (2025) *White Paper for European Defence – Readiness 2030*, [EC](#), 19 March 2025.

⁵⁷ Sebastian Clapp, Martin Höflmayer, Elena Lazarou & Marianna Pari (2025) *ReArm Europe Plan/Readiness 2030*, [European Parliamentary Research Service \(EPRS\)](#), Briefing PE 769.566, April 2025.

⁵⁸ European Commission (2025) 'EU Member States endorse €150 billion SAFE defence loan instrument

Strategy.⁵⁹ These initiatives provide an opportunity to revive Europe's defense industry, accelerate capability manufacturing, and create opportunities to integrate Ukraine's defense industry in various cooperation formats.⁶⁰ This would not only enhance support for Ukraine but also allow Kyiv to become an important defense partner of EU and NATO in the future, provided that Kyiv lifts the military equipment export ban.⁶¹

The US government should take into account these intra-EU developments to see how the EU can support NATO's goals, aligning with Washington's overall goal to reorient resources toward Asia. If the US remains engaged and supports Europe throughout this process, it will incentivize European NATO allies to take greater responsibility for their security, especially given the existence of necessary enabling frameworks and strategies at the EU level as mentioned above. The European governments, at the same time, will need to continue their efforts to effectively communicate the political reasons for increased defense spending to their constituencies. While it is too soon to evaluate whether the summit managed to "equalize" the burden-sharing between NATO allies, it still demonstrated that the US matters to Europe and vice versa. Also, contrary to the rhetoric of some of the members of

to boost European defence capabilities,' [EC](#), 27 May 2025.

⁵⁹ European Commission (2025) 'EDIS: Our Common Defence Industrial Strategy,' EC, [accessed 16 July 2025](#)

⁶⁰ Liana Fix and Rebecca Lissner (2025) "Weathering the Storm: The Hague Summit and the

the current US administration, many Americans still support the idea of Washington playing a leading role in global affairs, reject isolationism and are against withdrawal from NATO.⁶²

A strategic approach of the US government would include a policy that maintains leadership within NATO while supporting European allies in their efforts to become more self-reliant in terms of defense and security and to maintain the support for Ukraine on this path. The way forward towards a more robust European pillar within NATO should be managed in an orderly process that would allow a path towards more equal burden-sharing and a gradual shift towards more European responsibility within NATO. To ensure this, effective communications between the US and the European partners will remain essential.

4. Conclusions

The Hague Summit was a decisive meeting aimed at addressing Europe's rearmament and responding to multiple challenges, including Washington's shifting focus on domestic issues and competition with China, as well as the growing security threats posed by Russia's invasion of Ukraine. NATO allies committed to significantly boosting their defense spending and avoided clashes with the Trump

Future of NATO," [Council on Foreign Relations \(CFR\)](#), 17 June 2025.

⁶¹ Melania Parzonka (2025) "What Europe can gain from Ukrainian arms exports," [Politico](#), 28 May 2025.

⁶² The Ronald Reagan Presidential Foundation and Institute (RRPFI) (2025) "2025 Reagan Institute Summer Survey." [RRPFI](#) Summer 2025

administration. Yet many questions were left unresolved, leaving a sense of uncertainty about NATO's deterrence posture and its ability to adapt to emerging threats.

Concerning burden-sharing, the 5% GDP defense spending pledge signals European willingness to take greater responsibility for their security. However, the lack of full consensus and Spain's opt-out risk setting a precedent that could weaken implementation. To translate pledges into real capabilities, European allies will need to align spending increases with practical capability development and transparency to sustain public support. This will also strengthen the perception in the United States - not only in the administration but also within Congress - that the European allies are a reliable partner within NATO and resolved to strengthen deterrence in the face of the threat from Russia.

With regards to Ukraine, the summit's sidelining of critical discussions about Ukraine's defense and NATO membership path reflects ongoing divisions within the Alliance. However, sustaining Ukraine's defense remains vital for European and transatlantic security. NATO allies should clearly define their support mechanisms for Ukraine while aligning them with European rearmament timelines, ensuring that Kyiv's needs are integrated into Europe's broader security architecture.

With respect to the US role, President Trump's ambiguous stance on the US' long-term commitment to European security and Article 5 will remain an issue of concern for all NATO members. While behind closed doors assurances were provided and European allies

might feel reassured in the short to mid-term, the ball is still in their court to translate NATO Summit commitments into practical and tangible results. However, continued US engagement, even if reduced, will remain critical for NATO's credibility and deterrence.

In terms of NATO-EU cooperation, the summit underscored the importance of accelerating collaboration to strengthen Europe's defense industrial base and autonomous capabilities while maintaining transatlantic interoperability. EU frameworks like the Readiness 2030 plan and the SAFE instrument should be leveraged to align European investments with NATO capability needs, ensuring European allies can step up in defense while reducing overreliance on US systems and capabilities.

Overall, the Hague Summit demonstrated European NATO allies' intent to take greater responsibility for its security while preserving transatlantic unity, but several critical issues need to be addressed in order to sustain and improve deterrence. Moving forward, NATO and the EU should coordinate burden-sharing metrics and defense industrial strategies, ensure structured dialogue with the US on future posture and commitments to Europe, and establish clear pathways to sustain support for Ukraine. Only through such coordinated efforts can NATO maintain credible deterrence and adapt effectively to an evolving security landscape challenged by Russia, China, and other actors.

5. Policy Recommendations

To ensure that the Hague Summit outcomes will truly improve NATO's deterrence, it is essential that the European NATO members build on the decisions made while addressing the questions that remain unanswered. Among key priorities requiring further action are:

1. Operationalize the 5% GDP defense spending, ensuring close alignment with the NATO capability targets and existing gaps among European NATO allies.
2. Continue to identify key capability gaps and dependencies of the European NATO members on the US (such as strategic enablers) with the aim of reducing these gaps through targeted investment and cooperation.
3. Clarify the scope of 1,5% GDP spending on defense and security-oriented projects and closely related areas to ensure that they make a meaningful contribution towards NATO's collective goals. This includes preventing the use of creative accounting practices and discouraging the funding of purely national initiatives that do not enhance the allies' interoperability, readiness, or collective defense capabilities.
4. Clarify whether and to what extent the military support to Ukraine provided by individual NATO allies counts as the 5% GDP defense spending benchmark in order to avoid confusion and ensure consistency.
5. Ensure that member states do not inflate the reported value of the military assistance provided to Ukraine, for example through a centralized system (e.g. in the framework of NSATU) to promote comparability, accountability and transparency.
6. Maintain close coordination and communications between the US administration and other NATO allies in order to understand potential changes and adjustments in the US force posture; and develop strategies of how other NATO allies should respond in the event of a significant withdrawal of US assets and capabilities from Europe.
7. Seek consensus with the US administration on the future participation and limits of the US defense industry in the European defense market, with the goal of addressing the most urgent critical capability gaps in Europe. This may include the promotion of joint enterprises between European and US manufacturers.
8. Reinforce NATO-EU coordination and strengthen EU mechanisms and frameworks for promoting cooperation and harmonization in the European defense industrial base.
9. Maintain, reinforce and institutionalize Western support to Ukraine, using NATO and EU frameworks, the Ukraine Defense Contact Group and the PURL initiative.
10. Leverage battlefield knowledge gained by Ukraine and consider investing into relevant, proven and effective capabilities.
11. Incentivize the creation of joint enterprises, including with and within Ukraine, to enable joint procurement, enhance interoperability and provide practical support to Ukraine and its

defense sector, while gaining significant benefits for European and wider NATO defense industries.

12. Develop a coherent and coordinated policy vis-à-vis Russia that aligns with efforts to achieve sustainable peace based on international law, Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity. To this end, NATO allies and other international partners (such as in the G7 framework) should continue to closely cooperate and tighten sanctions against Russia, secure substantial, sustained support for Ukraine (potentially using Russia's

frozen assets), and raise the cost for Russia to continue its war of aggression.

13. Develop and maintain effective strategic communications and share relevant information with the wider public to make sure that European citizens are well-informed about the increased defense spending, actions taken by NATO allies, and the need to strengthen NATO's deterrence. This will also be pivotal during national elections, when increased defense spending will likely become a controversial topic.

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